

Synthesis of 3-Phenyl-4-arylidine-5-*o*-hydroxyphenylpyrazoles

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Several new 3-phenyl-4-arylidine-5-*o*-hydroxyphenylpyrazoles (2) have been synthesised directly by the action of hydrazine hydrate and 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-aryl-acrylophenones (1). Their structures have been supported on the basis of elemental analysis and ir spectral analysis.

PYRAZOLES with only one exception do not occur in nature. Various substituted pyrazoles are reported in literature. Literature survey reveals that certain pyrazole derivatives show wide ranging activity¹⁻⁵. One of the important methods of pyrazole synthesis involves the reaction of 1,3-diketones with hydrazine derivatives. Substituted pyrazoles with arylidene moiety at 4-position are not reported so far. It therefore appeared interesting to synthesise pyrazoles containing arylidene moiety. The present paper describes the synthesis of 3-phenyl-4-arylidine-5-*o*-hydroxyphenylpyrazoles.

When the condensation of 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-phenylacrylophenone with hydrazine hydrate has been carried out in boiling acetic acid, a product crystallised from ethanol (m.p. 185°) has been isolated. The identity of the product 2a has been established on the basis of usual chemical properties.

Several other products (2b-2i) have been synthesised by the extension of the above reaction by varying the substituent R at position-3 (Table 1).

a ; Phenyl
c ; *p*-Chlorophenyl
e ; *p*-Anisyl
g ; 2-Pyridyl
i ; 4-Pyridyl

b ; *o*-Chlorophenyl
d ; *p*-Bromophenyl
f ; *p*-Nitrophenyl
h ; 3-Pyridyl

Experimental

The required *o*-hydroxydibenzoylmethane was prepared following earlier known procedure⁶. The 2'-hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-aryl acrylophenones⁷ (1)

TABLE 1—3-PHENYL-4-ARYLIDINE-*o*-HYDROXYPHENYLPYRAZOLES

Sl. no.	2'-Hydroxy-2-benzoyl-3-aryl-acrylophenones (1)	3-Phenyl-5- <i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl-4-arylidine-pyrazoles (2)	M. p. °C	Analysis N % : Found/(Calcd.)
1.	3-Phenyl (1a)	4-Phenyl (2a)	185	8.45 (8.64)
2.	3- <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl (1b)	4- <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl (2b)	175	7.62 (7.82)
3.	3- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl (1c)	4- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl (2c)	225	7.34 (7.82)
4.	3- <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl (1d)	4- <i>p</i> -Bromophenyl (2d)	244	6.45 (6.94)
5.	3- <i>p</i> -Anisyl (1e)	4- <i>p</i> -Anisyl (2e)	240	7.43 (7.90)
6.	3- <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl (1f)	4- <i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl (2f)	205	7.27 (7.58)
7.	3-(2-Pyridyl) (1g)	4-(2-Pyridyl) (2g)	116 d	8.05 (8.66)
8.	3-(3-Pyridyl) (1h)	4-(3-Pyridyl) (2h)	206	8.11 (8.66)
9.	3-(4-Pyridyl) (1i)	4-(4-Pyridyl) (2i)	174	8.16 (8.66)

Satisfactory C and H found in all cases.

were prepared by the interaction of *o*-hydroxy-dibenzoylmethane and aldehydes in boiling ethanol in the presence of a few drops of piperidine.

3-Phenyl-4-arylidine 5-*o*-hydroxyphenylpyrazoles : Details of a typical experiment (where, R=R'=phenyl) are as follows. A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-2-benzyl-3-aryl-acrylophenone (0.65 g, 0.002 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (15%, 5 ml) was refluxed in acetic acid for 1 h. It was cooled and diluted with water, and a solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 185° (Found: C, 81.1, H, 4.32; N, 8.45. C₂₂H₁₆ON₂ calcd. for, C, 81.5; H, 4.94; N, 8.64%); gave positive test for nitrogen; soluble in dilute sodium hydroxide; have a bright red colour with FeCl₃ solution; ν_{max} 1 570 (C=N)^s, 1 480 (C=C), 3 040 (OH) and 985 cm⁻¹ (pyrazole ring)^{s,9}.

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